

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTER-FAT

By S. MUKHERJEE AND M. GOSWAMI

Development of rancidity on butter-fat on storage with different chemicals has been studied. Effect of hydrogen passed into the butter-fat at room temperature has been investigated. The dissolved hydrogen has been found to stop hydrolytic rancidity of butter-fat for a period of 5 months and to retard oxidative rancidity to a very great extent.

The prevention of rancidity in edible fats is a problem of vast importance which has not yet been solved. The reasons assigned for deterioration of fats are generally oxygen, light, temperature, moisture, micro-organisms, materials of the container and above all, the unsaturated glycerides and the lower glycerides which on decomposition give the rancid odour. The mechanism of the decomposition has been the subject of various communications but it cannot be said that it has been as yet cleared. The only thing that has been achieved is that with addition of certain substances, both natural and synthetic, called antioxidants, it has been possible to retard the decomposition for a certain period. The uses of the synthetic antioxidants are limited in case of edible oils, as many of them are toxic. Lea (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1936, 55, 293r) examined and proposed for this purpose, citric and allied type of acids and several amino-acids. Natural antioxidants, prepared from vegetable oils, have been also used by Matill and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2204). Gossypol, among the antioxidants was shown by Matill to be much superior. Coe (*Oil & Soap*, 1930, 15, 230) claimed catalase preparations to be much more effective as antioxidants than the pyrogallol derivatives. Numerous works have been done on the use of synthetic antioxidants for retarding rancidity, and for edible fats, especially butter-fat, the use of ethyl gallate (0.005 to 0.02%) has been recommended by Lea. Recently Banerjee has shown that Kamala dye (*Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 559) is an effective antioxidant for butter-fat. Davis (*J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News Ed.*, 1940, 3, 124) has shown the efficacy of cereal flour paste.

The term rancidity has been for a long time used to represent two entirely different changes which take place in fats and oils: (i) the hydrolysis of the glycerides with liberation of free fatty acid, and (ii) the oxidation of fats and oils containing unsaturated acids resulting in the formation of aldehydes, ketones, acids of lower molecular weights and organic peroxides. In general, the two phenomena of hydrolytic and oxidative rancidity proceed simultaneously, so that practically no sharp line of demarcation can be drawn from the practical point of view.

In the process of hydrolytic rancidity there is always an increase in titratable acidity, and determination of acid value is adopted to follow the course of hydrolysis of glycerides. The most practical assessment of oxidative rancidity is by organoleptic tests, based on taste reports. Whilst development of flavours is generally accepted as the ultimate criterion of stability, organoleptic tests are less easy to control than tests of a more definitely chemical nature. The course of oxidative rancidity is usually therefore followed by determination of Kries number and the peroxide value, based respectively on the presence of epihydrin aldehyde $\begin{array}{c} | \\ \text{—O—} \\ | \end{array}$ $(\text{CH}_2 - \text{CH} \cdot \text{CHO})$ and organic peroxides in fats; the latter is regarded as the most suitable quantitative measure of this type of rancidity though the Kries number, which is extremely useful for qualitative purposes, has also been regarded as semi-quantitative.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The Kries number was determined by the method of Walters, Muers and Anderson (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1938, 57, 53r) with a little modification as follows: 3 ml. of melted fat were weighed in a test-tube and diluted to 5 c. c. with amyl acetate to which was added 1 ml. of a 0.5% solution of phloroglucinol in amyl acetate and 2 ml. of trichloroacetic acid solution in amyl acetate ($x \text{ g./}0.382 x \text{ ml.}$). The resultant mixture was stirred for 3 to 4 seconds by bubbling a stream of air and the test-tube then warmed in a bath at 45° for exactly 15 minutes. The mixture was then diluted with 8 c. c. of a mixture of amyl acetate and alcohol (1 : 1) and colour matched in a Lovibond tintometer. The Kries number (T) is given by the following expression,

$$T = \frac{R}{lc}$$

where R = reading in the Lovibond tintometer; l = length of the cell, c = conc. of the oil in total solution in g./c.c.

The addition of a mixture of alcohol and amyl acetate (1 : 1) instead of amyl acetate in diluting the mixture has the advantage that it stabilises the colour for about 10 minutes, which otherwise begins to decompose gradually in the reaction mixture.

The peroxide value was estimated by the modified Wheeler and Paschke method (*Oil & Soap*, 1944, 21, 33) in which the reaction was carried out in an atmosphere of CO_2 . The peroxide value is expressed as the number of c.c. of $N/200$ -thio per g. of the sample.

This paper has mainly been devoted to the study of the development of rancidity on butter-fat on storage with different chemicals. In the first set of experiments the fat was kept both in presence and absence of moisture and in presence of casein and lactose (1% each). The effect of vanillin (0.05%) and that of passing hydrogen gas at room temperature was also studied. These results are given in Tables IA and Ib.

in absence and presence of moisture retards rancidity of butter-fat; (d) the behaviour of vanillin is somewhat curious: whilst it increases the acidity of the fat to a much greater extent than all the substances in the table, it suppresses the figure for the Kries number and peroxide value to a much greater extent *i.e.* it probably retards formation of Kries active substance and organic peroxides, and lastly (e) hydrogen even in presence of moisture seems to be the best retarder of rancidity with respect to both hydrolytic and oxidative rancidity.

In the light of conclusion (a) above, it therefore seemed plausible to carry out the subsequent experiments with completely dry fats. But, since the fats of commerce are invariably associated with a certain amount of moisture, the percentage widely varying, and since majority of foods contains fat in an aqueous phase, the study of the problem of rancidity with anhydrous fats will be of little use from a practical standpoint. Hence, the subsequent storage experiments were all carried out in presence of moisture, after having first ascertained that moisture accelerated the hydrolytic decomposition of glycerides of fatty acids.

Unsaturation in fats has always been a factor in the process of oxidative rancidity in fats and it is well known that reduction of unsaturation by hydrogenation produces fats that keep much better than the mother oils. Selective nature of hydrogenation is well known, and many experimenters have observed that by hydrogenation up to the oleic acid or even to the linoleic acid stage, fats can be obtained with much increased keeping qualities. The experiment No. 5 in Table I with hydrogen was carried out with the simple idea that if instead of having the hydrogen in actual combination with the unsaturated fatty acid molecules, it would be possible to retard rancidity by merely having the hydrogen in a state of dissolution. We have already seen how much hydrogen retards the rancidity, both oxidative and hydrolytic.

TABLE II

Effect of passing hydrogen at diff. temp. for 2 hours.

Description.	Initial.			After 40 days.			After 60 days.			After 100 days.			After 150 days.		
	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.
1. H ₂ passed at 30°	0.46	0.4	0.0	0.743	16.4	0.0	0.781	1.99	0.15	0.882	2.2	0.42	0.912	2.8	0.454
2. H ₂ passed at 40°	"	"	"	0.789	1.52	0.0	0.749	1.82	0.15	0.784	2.0	0.41	0.899	2.61	0.455
3. H ₂ passed at 50°	"	"	"	0.504	1.42	0.0	0.812	1.50	0.05	0.537	1.9	0.25	0.599	2.0	0.262
4. H ₂ passed at 60°	"	"	"	0.470	1.30	0.0	0.484	1.42	0.0	0.502	1.8	0.15	0.545	2.0	0.208
5. H ₂ passed at 70°	"	"	"	0.672	1.55	0.0	0.689	1.81	0.0	0.733	2.1	0.32	0.802	2.4	0.419
6. H ₂ passed at 80°	"	"	"	0.674	1.55	0.0	0.697	1.82	0.15	0.766	2.1	0.39	0.846	2.4	0.426
7. H ₂ passed at 90°	"	"	"	0.670	1.60	0.0	0.697	1.66	0.15	0.766	2.2	0.4	0.850	2.6	0.487
8. Control	"	"	"	0.674	2.12	0.20	1.24	2.58	0.48	1.847	2.9	1.0	3.02	4.1	2.86

The next series of experiments were carried out with fats in association with moisture through which hydrogen gas was passed for a period of two hours at temperatures 40°, 50°, 60°, 70°, 80° and 90° with the obvious idea of increasing the solubility of hydrogen in the fat (Grimm, *Inter. Conf. Bituminous Coal*, 1931, II, 49).

The experimental results are given in Table II. It may be seen that up to 40 days there is no rise in peroxide value at any of the temperatures but after that it gradually increases and it is minimum at 60°, above which it rises. Kries number and acid value after 40 days are minimum at 60°, and with storage in general they gradually increase but nevertheless they are minimum at the said temperature even after a period of 150 days. When compared with the control sample it would thus appear that hydrogen has a retarding effect both as regards Kries number and peroxide value.

Further experiments with hydrogen was carried out to observe the effect of storage with this gas under a positive pressure. The experiments were carried out at 30° 50° and 70°, hydrogen being passed for 2 hours and then the samples stored under pressure in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The results are given in Table III and it would be seen that storage with positive pressure does not further improve the result as detailed in Table II. Simultaneously with the

TABLE III

Effect of passing hydrogen under pressure at diff. temp.

Description.	Initial.			After 30 days.			After 60 days.			After 90 days.			After 120 days.		
	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.
1. H ₂ passed at 60° for 4 hrs.	0.45	0.4	0.0	0.504	1.42	0.0	0.512	1.50	0.05	0.597	1.9	0.25	0.589	2.0	0.262
2. H ₂ passed under pressure at 30°	"	"	"	0.798	1.52	0.05	0.778	1.78	0.22	0.76	2.1	0.64	0.87	2.5	0.92
3. H ₂ passed under pressure at 50°	"	"	"	0.523	1.30	0.0	0.623	1.45	0.05	0.76	2.0	0.35	0.832	2.5	0.48
4. H ₂ passed under pressure at 70°	"	"	"	0.852	1.55	0.10	0.697	1.73	0.20	0.794	2.0	0.52	0.872	2.52	0.90
5. Control	"	"	"	0.874	2.1	0.20	1.24	2.58	0.48	1.84	2.6	0.98	2.52	3.6	2.45

above set of experiments, storage of the fat in atmospheres of CO₂ and N₂ at the room temperature was carried out, the respective gases being also passed for a period of 2 hours (Table IV). The results show that inert atmosphere has in general a retarding effect, but still hydrogen gives better result.

TABLE IV

Effect of storage of butter-fat under different gas packages.

Description.	Initial.			After 30 days.			After 60 days.			After 90 days.			After 120 days.		
	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.
1. CO ₂	0.45	0.4	0.0	0.75	2.1	0.15	0.76	2.58	0.32	0.86	2.6	0.51	0.98	3.6	0.64
2. Nitrogen	"	"	"	0.65	2.0	0.10	0.72	2.58	0.20	0.86	2.6	0.32	0.97	3.6	0.53
3. Hydrogen	"	"	"	0.74	1.84	0.0	0.78	1.88	0.15	0.86	2.2	0.42	0.91	2.5	0.45
4. Control	"	"	"	0.87	2.1	0.20	1.24	2.58	0.48	1.84	2.6	0.98	2.52	3.6	2.45

TABLE V

Effect of different antioxidants on butter-fat at room temperature.

Antioxidants.	Initial.		After 30 days.		After 60 days.		After 90 days.		After 120 days.					
	A.V.	K.N. P.V.	A.V.	K.N. P.V.	A.V.	K.N. P.V.	A.V.	K.N. P.V.	A.V.	K.N. P.V.				
1. Catechol	0.45	0.4	0.764	1.18	0.10	0.898	1.50	0.188	0.894	2.1	0.310	1.0	2.55	0.289
2. Pyrocatechol	"	"	0.768	1.17	0.06	0.835	1.49	0.20	0.898	2.08	0.247	1.07	2.51	0.351
3. Hydroquinone	"	"	0.768	1.17	0.06	0.831	1.49	0.167	0.927	2.0	0.187	1.022	2.50	0.338
4. Pyrogallol	"	"	0.878	0.85	0.03	0.877	0.94	0.065	0.774	1.01	0.10	0.852	1.04	0.121
5. Gallic acid	"	"	0.859	1.3	0.08	0.854	1.54	0.16	0.783	2.14	0.30	0.878	2.7	0.420
6. Pyrocatechuic acid	"	"	0.721	1.15	0.05	0.805	1.40	0.157	0.894	1.80	0.196	0.969	2.18	0.334
7. Oxalic acid	"	"	0.690	1.01	0.15	0.892	1.23	0.324	1.027	1.5	0.593	1.204	1.9	0.754
8. Maleic acid	"	"	0.784	1.17	0.17	0.841	1.8	0.40	0.927	2.10	0.542	1.044	2.44	0.672
9. Malonic acid	"	"	0.502	1.16	0.15	0.777	1.54	0.20	0.927	2.18	0.45	1.065	2.63	0.704
10. Coumarin	"	"	0.788	1.20	0.15	0.874	1.8	0.39	1.56	2.66	0.62	2.40	3.4	1.602
11. Tartaric acid	"	"	0.724	1.23	0.12	0.776	1.6	0.347	0.893	2.15	0.513	1.16	2.66	0.949
12. Citric acid	"	"	0.758	1.20	0.10	0.847	1.52	0.25	0.868	2.10	0.36	0.964	2.6	0.568
13. Sod. Pot. tartrate	"	"	0.680	1.22	0.12	0.714	1.7	0.31	0.732	2.3	0.419	0.804	2.65	0.502
14. Sod. citrate	"	"	0.690	1.08	0.05	0.743	1.44	0.15	0.765	1.94	0.306	0.876	2.30	0.370
15. Control	"	"	0.874	2.1	0.20	1.24	2.58	0.48	1.84	2.9	0.68	2.52	3.5	2.45

Considering the most important groups of antioxidants that are generally used in the preservation of foods we find that compounds rich in hydroxyl groups,

especially the phenolic and enolic in character, are predominant. We therefore studied the effect of a few substances of the quinol group, the pyrogallol group and also some of the acidic antioxidants and their salts (Table V). It may be seen that the polyhydroxy compound, pyrogallol exerts maximum effect of retardation. Then comes catechol and hydroquinone. Among the acids and their salts, the effect of sodium citrate and sodium potassium tartrate is maximum.

The experiments on the antioxidant studies were carried out by fortifying the fat with vitamins A and C (Table VI). It is seen that combination of the vitamins produces the desirable result.

TABLE VI

Butter fat kept in presence of vitamin A & C.

Description.	Initial.			After 30 days.			After 60 days.			After 90 days.			After 120 days.		
	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.	A.V.	K.N.	P.V.
1. Ascorbic acid (0.1%)	0.45	0.4	0.0	0.721	1.4	0.0	0.784	1.64	0.06	0.828	1.9	0.20	0.922	2.2	0.86
2. α -Tocopherol acetate (0.005%)	..	..	..	0.715	1.45	0.0	0.748	1.68	0.02	0.794	2.0	0.05	0.888	2.3	0.075
3. Ascorbic acid (0.1%) + α -tocopherol acetate (0.002%)	..	..	..	0.703	1.20	0.0	0.715	1.24	0.0	0.718	1.3	0.05	0.738	1.45	0.064
4. Control	..	..	..	0.674	2.1	0.2	1.24	2.58	0.48	1.64	2.9	0.98	2.52	3.6	2.45

Most experiments on antioxidant studies are carried out at temperatures ranging from 70° to 110°, and in presence of other accelerating factors; but very few of the experimental conditions resemble those actually encountered in practice, since it is quite apparent that the antioxidants may be affected appreciably by changes in the condition of testing, and there has been some confusion in interpreting the results carried out at higher temperatures. Of course, there is no denying in the fact that the antioxidants, which protect fats at higher temperatures, will also be able to protect them at ordinary temperatures. But there also exist some exceptions. The experiments in this paper were carried out at room temperature and time required to reach a peroxide value of 2 ml. per g. was regarded as end of the induction period. The protection factor with the best of the antioxidants are given approximately in Table VII. The concentration of the antioxidants used in these experiments was 0.02%.

TABLE VII

Protection factors of some antioxidants with respect to butter-fat.

Antioxidants.	Conc.	Protection factor.	Antioxidants.	Conc.	Protection factor.
Pyrogallol	0.02%	6.2	Hydroquinol	0.02%	5.5
Hydrogen (60°)	—	6.0	Sodium citrate	0.10	4.85
Catechol	0.02	5.8	Oxalic acid	0.10	2.7
Gallic acid	0.02	5.6	Coumarin	0.10	0.4
Pyrocatechol	0.02	5.5			

DISCUSSION

The effect of dissolved hydrogen on retardation of rancidity of butter-fat is very remarkable as it appears from Tables I, II and III. Whilst hydrogen practically stops the hydrolytic rancidity of butter-fat for a period of five months

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

(Fig. 1), it simultaneously retards the oxidative rancidity to a very great extent. Organoleptic rancidity, however, becomes evident at the end of this period. The behaviour of hydrogen with butter-fat as regards protection is most marked with its increase in solubility with rise of temperature up to 50° to 60° above which the diminished action is probably due to the accelerating effect of temperature on

rancidity (Fig. 2). Storage with hydrogen under pressure at the different temperature does not, however, offer any additional protection to the fat (Fig. 3).

The experiments on gas packing with H₂, N₂ and CO₂ with simultaneous

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

passage of the gas for 2 hours show a marked improvement on keeping quality as regards peroxide (Fig. 3) and acid values. We know that oxygen is necessary in order to produce the oxidative rancidity and that rancidity is primarily due to the presence of dissolved oxygen in the fat and it is this dissolved oxygen that activates the water molecules as also affects the unsaturated acids resulting in hydrolytic and peroxidic rancidity. In the light of the above experimental results (Tables II & III) it is well to presume that the dissolved hydrogen immobilises the activity of oxygen molecules probably thus :

An examination of Table V reveals that polyphenolic antioxidants, especially pyrogallol and gallic acid, are the most efficient retarder of rancidity of butter-fat. The behaviour of pyrogallol may be assumed to be due to its very enhanced affinity for oxygen. The salts of the organic acids are more marked in behaviour than the parent acids (Fig. 5). This is, however, contrary to the observation of Greenbank and Holm (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1934, 25, 242). Coumarin is almost inactive (Fig. 4). Hydrogen (60°) (Table VII) secures a very high place in the list of antioxidants and large scale experiments on preservation of fats with this reagent is worth attempting.

Of the vitamins tested, α -tocopherol acetate (quinol group) and l-ascorbic acid, we find that the former is a very good antioxidant in as much it is a fat-soluble vitamin. Ascorbic acid is much less active (Fig. 6), though a very good synergistic effect is observed when used in combination with α -tocopherol. A difficulty in the

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

use of ascorbic acid as an antioxidant is that it is insoluble in fats. The fact that the ester of l-ascorbic acid with fatty acids like palmitic and stearic are quite fat-soluble, makes its incorporation much easier in such forms. The behaviour of these fatty acid esters of ascorbic acid with butter-fat will be published in a later communication.

APPLIED CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE &
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received January 10, 1947.